

A Secure and Efficient IoT Enabled Communication with Nearby Alerting System for Tracing Vehicles on Emergency

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Abstract

With the help of IoT services, our daily lives may become smarter, easier, and safer. A lifeline system might be created by utilising the Internet of Things (IoT) in the design of a few outstanding administrations. Making the most of one's time is crucial in today's hectic world. Students may have to wait a lot longer for the arrival of their school bus or van. There are a number of communication advances that may be used to make sure time is being used efficiently. Regardless, they aren't set up to provide the kind of useful help that students need. With the help of emerging technologies like the internet of things (IoT), this article details the development of a school bus monitoring system that may provide practical forms of aid. In this research, we provide an Internet of Things (IoT) enabled method that may provide area following administrations and crisis correspondence in a remote car that encounters a tragic accident or other crisis situation. The framework could be physically activated or start running automatically after an incident or catastrophe. The suggested Internet of Things (IoT) system maintains tabs on the car by combining RFID and GPS technologies. Apart from that, a prediction is made for the school bus's arrival season using RFID and GSM technology. This method supports an easy-to-understand arrangement, which ensures a beneficial technique that operates on life. Timely response and medical assistance will be provided in the event of an emergency. Accurate and efficient real-time

monitoring of the target region is also possible with the suggested approach.

Keywords--Internet of Things (IoT), RFID, GPS & GSM

Introduction

When two or more locations are not physically linked by an electrical wire, they are engaging in wireless communication. Internet of Things (IoT) devices that have Wi-Fi connectivity enable communication between machines. This technology transfers data from industrial machinery to mobile devices, whether they be wearable or wireless, and then processes that data over a network. Even though the sensor and actuator are physically located in separate locations, they are able to communicate with one another over an internet network. A VTS, or vehicle tracking system, may be constructed with the use of IoT techniques. A In order to get a complete picture of where all of the cars are, vehicle tracking systems employ a combination of automated vehicle location systems for individual vehicles and software that gathers data from the whole fleet. While global positioning systems (GPS) are the most popular in today's car tracking systems, other forms of automated vehicle location technologies are also available. over the use of dedicated software, vehicle data may be accessed on digital maps over the internet. Since the advent of global positioning systems (GPS) in 1978, vehicle tracking has been an established practice. In 1996, President Bill Clinton decided that the Global Positioning technology (GPS) would be useful

for both the military and civilians, despite the fact that the technology was first developed with the military in mind. In an intelligent city, all devices, or more accurately, everything, is constantly linked to the ubiquitous network. They are able to converse with one another despite differences in communication protocols and software/hardware environments. The use of machine-to-machine (M2M) communication is on the rise as a means to increase machine intelligence and facilitate data sharing. Using the idea of a smart city, we have developed a system that can save the life of a smart car in the event of a roadside emergency. The term "Internet of things" (IOT) refers to the network connectivity that allows various physical devices, cars, buildings, and other objects to collect and share data via the use of embedded software, sensors, actuators, and system availability. The Internet of Things (IoT) creates opportunities for the physical world to be more easily integrated into computer-based systems, which in turn improves efficiency, accuracy, economic benefit, and reduces the need for human intervention by allowing items to be detected or controlled remotely across existing system infrastructure. You can't link the real world to the internet until you use IoT.

Wireless communication occurs when two or more places are not physically connected by an electrical cable. Devices connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) via Wi-Fi allow machines to communicate with one another. This innovation allows for the transmission of data from industrial equipment to wireless or wearable mobile devices, which are then processed via a network. Sensor and actuator may be in different physical places, but they may still talk to each other over the internet. Using methods from the Internet of Things, a VTS (vehicle tracking system) may be built. A

Autonomous vehicle location systems (AVLS) for specific vehicles and fleet-wide data collection software work together in

vehicle tracking systems to provide a comprehensive picture of the vehicles' whereabouts. While most modern automobile tracking systems use global positioning systems (GPS), there are other automated vehicle locating technologies on the market. Vehicle data may be accessible on digital maps over the internet using specialised software. The technique of tracking vehicles has been around since the introduction of GPS in 1978. Although GPS was originally designed for military use, President Bill Clinton determined in 1996 that it may be beneficial for both civilians and the military. Every single element in an intelligent city is always connected to the pervasive network. In spite of disparities in communication protocols and software/hardware setups, they can nonetheless have a conversation. M2M communication is becoming more popular as a way to improve machine intelligence and make data exchange easier. We have created a system that can rescue a smart vehicle from a dead end in a roadside emergency by using the concept of a smart city. By using embedded software, sensors, actuators, and system availability, the "Internet of things" (IOT) enables many physical items, vehicles, and buildings to gather and exchange data via network connection. By facilitating the remote detection and control of objects across preexisting system infrastructure, the Internet of Things (IoT) makes it possible to better integrate the physical world with computer-based systems, which in turn increases efficiency, accuracy, economic benefit, and decreases the need for human intervention. Until you implement IoT, you will not be able to connect the physical world to the web.

Fig.1 : GPS based tracking system

GPS vehicle following guarantees their security as voyaging. This vehicle subsequent scaffold is exploit as a part of customer's vehicles as a burglary avoidance and safeguard gadget. The cryptogram transmitted by the following scaffold are exploit by vehicle owner or police to find a steal vehicle in equivalent the stolen vehicle motor speed going to receded and pushed to off. Engine can't restart without consent of the secret key when it is switch of by following framework. This scaffold initiate for vehicle following normally handle as a part of naval force administrators for naval force administration work, send off, steering, on board data and security. It can be utilized to screen driving execution of a parent with a high schooled driver. To forestall burglary in purchaser vehicles vehicle following framework is utilized.

Survey & Analysis

An improved traffic control system using Raspberry pi and RFID technologies was proposed by Manasi Patil et al. A raspberry pi controller is embedded in the car and communicates with sensors such as gas, temperature, and shock detectors. The value of these sensors is set before an accident happens. One sensor's value changes in the event of an accident, and a message is transmitted by GSM to a specified number (the ambulance's). The vehicle's position is also sent via the GPS module, which is likewise connected to the controller. It is necessary to give the ambulance with a clear path once it receives the notification. The RFID tag transmits electromagnetic waves over an interface with the ambulance's controller ARM. The RFID reader, mounted on the joints, picks up the tag's electromagnetic waves as soon as the ambulance approaches the traffic light. In a very short amount of time, the readers check the database and change the status of the traffic light from red to green. The RFID on the other joint will automatically flip the light red under these circumstances. The path to the ambulance is now clearly marked. A system for driving safety that relies on accelerometers was created by V.Sagar Reddy and colleagues. The system's main selling point is that it can identify or monitor the whereabouts of automobiles with the simple transmission of an SMS or email to the designated recipient. In order to quickly access

the accelerometer for event detection, the system is built utilising the Raspberry Pi (ARM11). In the event that anything happens, the notification should be transmitted to the appropriate authority so that they can act quickly to prevent further harm and preserve lives. The person in charge, like the car's owner, gets an email with the images taken by the camera, together with details about the accident and when it happened. [2]. A system that uses GPS and GSM modems to automatically detect and message about vehicle accidents was suggested by Sri Krishna Chaitanya Varma et al. In the system, an AT89C52 microcontroller is used. The power supply is shown by the LED being on when the system is turned on. Whenever the infrared sensors detect an obstruction, they trigger an interrupt to be sent to the microcontroller. When an accident occurs, the GPS system takes the coordinates of the offending car and relays them. A text message containing this data is sent to a mobile phone. The GSM modem that is connected to the circuit is used to receive this message. The coordinates of the north and south poles are included in the communiqué. It is possible to approximate the vehicle's location using these data.

Methods for detecting car collisions and creating a remote alert device using Arduino were detailed by Apurva Mane et al. The real-time transmission of the vehicle's location (longitude, latitude), time, and angle to both the monitoring station and the user's or owner's mobile device should allow for the prompt retrieval of medical assistance in the event of an accident or theft, which is one of the design's key advantages. Additionally, the owner or user may see the current location of a car at any given moment. A system that may identify accidents using a smartphone's sensors (e.g., accelerometer) and broadcast accident information over the phone's 3G connection was presented by Thompson, Chris, et al. in. However, the system isn't totally automated, doesn't interface with the car, and sometimes requires a third-party reporter to provide comprehensive emergency details and images. General Motors' OnStar [13] smart assistance system aids drivers by directing them on routes and offering navigation services. Additionally, its always-connected 4G connection offers emergency communication options. However, local emergency rescue centres cannot be contacted via OnStar, only

Fig.2 : GPS in Vehicle with server

the vehicle's manufacturer or emergency

numbers (such as 911). This limitation might lead to a delay in rescue efforts.

Proposed Approach

For any kind of vehicle emergency, we have presented a method for position monitoring and emergency transmission in this article. By automatically notifying the closest hospital and police station, this technology strives to minimise damages if a vehicle encounters any unlucky event, such as an accident. In addition to helping with automotive problems, it is useful in cases of medical emergencies, criminal problems, civil emergencies, and so on. At the first sign of trouble, the car's emergency system kicks in (either automatically or manually, depending on the severity of the crisis) and notifies the control centre. Based on the kind of emergency, the location, and the nearest authority, the control room either automatically or manually sends the message to the closest rescue centre, which might be a hospital, police station, government office, or auto shop.

structures enable a base station to maintain track of the vehicles except the intervention of the driver where, as navigation machine helps the driver to attain the destination. Whether navigation device or tracking system, the architecture is greater or less similar. When an accident passed off in any area then GPS system tracks the role of the automobile and sends the information to the particular individual through GSM with the aid of alerting the man or woman through SMS or by using a call. As an additional option, the location detection can be achieved the usage of Google maps interface.

All different elements like the ultrasonic sensor, accelerometer and GPS and GSM modules are connected by means of STM32F

Fig.3 : Tracing system architecture

GPS - Global Positioning System Module is used in cars for each monitoring and navigation. Tracking

microcontroller. The code for the working of this machine is written in C. The LCD display displays brief messages to keep track of the working of the system. The alarm is

brought on when an accident is detected. Accelerometer is used to detect crash or rollover of the automobile and sends indicators when an accident happens to the microcontroller. The ultrasonic sensor detects whether or not the accident came about due to an obstacle.

A buzzer or beeper is a signaling device; it gives an audible warning when an accident occurs. If it is a false alarm or if the driver feels that he does no longer want instantaneous help, there is a switch in the system that he can use to quit the working of the system. Vibration sensor and carbon monoxide sensor both have a predefined threshold values set (in this case vibration degree of 60 and carbon monoxide range of 300). If that threshold value exceeds in the vehicle, the notification of emergency is sent to the administrator.

Results

Proposed emergency communication system is able to send automatic message to the control room with all relevant information of an emergency. A snap shot from the emergency control room is shown in fig. where the emergency location is shown in the map that helps the rescue team to reach the location at earliest. All nearby rescue centers are shown in the map and also the nearest one is calculated from the database. An automatic message is sent to them. There are buttons for the control room operator to send the message manually to other rescue centers if he thinks is required. The initial image taken by the car camera is

also shown in the interface that can help the authorities to understand the situation. An example screen shot of the control room Compared to other systems, it is a fully automated system that can automatically find out nearest rescue centers and send emergency message to them.

Conclusion

This method guarantees a beneficial strategy that operates on existence by supporting an easy-to-use arrangement. Not only is the

Approach	Model	Tracking efficiency	Target
Existing approach	Manual tracking	Moderate	Friends/Police station
Proposed approach	Location based	High	Nearby ambulance

vehicle simple to follow, but you'll also get timely alerts. In case of an emergency, there will be prompt action and treatment. The framework really comes into its own when it comes to preventing road accidents and making sure there are enough emergency vehicles. This method allows us to conduct crisis system and continuous vehicle surveillance. Because it is entirely automated, this system monitors the accident site and controls the traffic signals to guarantee that all individuals reach the emergency clinic in a timely manner. It is possible that this construction may be useful for transportation vehicles, particularly determined vehicles. We can easily track the automobile using this information. This paradigm enhances prosperity, safety, communication, and production when used in the business sector. Additional research and development may expand this industry to several sectors of safety and monitoring. Any area you choose may be watched precisely in real time with this technique.

References

[1] Manasi Patil, Aanchal Rawat, Prateek Singh, and Srishtie Dixit published an article titled "Accident Detection and Ambulance Control using Intelligent Traffic Control System" in the International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJETT) in April 2016.

**Volume 3, number 12 of the International Journal of Science, Engineering, and Technology Research (IJSETR) published an article titled "Design and Development of accelerometer based System for driver safety" in December 2014. The authors of the article were V. Sagar Reddy, L. Padma Sree, and V. Naveen Kumar.

the third The article "Automatic Vehicle Accident Detection And Messaging System Using GPS and GSM Modems" was published in August 2013 in the International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research and was written by Krishna Chaitanya Varma, Poornesh, Tarun Varma, and Harsha. Published in June 2014 in the International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology, the paper "Vehicle Collision detection and Remote Alarm Device using Arduino" was penned by Apurva Mane and Jaideep Rana.

Faculty members Bhagya Lakshmi V., Sanjeev M. Mhamane, and Savitha Hiremath published a paper in February 2014 called "FPGA Based Vehicle Tracking and Accident Warning using GPS" in the International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research. In their 2018 article "Multi-Vehicle Tracking With Road Maps and Car-Following Models" published in the IEEE Transaction on Intelligent Transport System, the authors Dan Song, Ratnasingham Tharmasarsa, Thigalingam Kirubajan, and Xavier N. Fernando discuss this topic. R.C. Jisha, Aiswarya Jyothindranath, and Sajitha Kumary's "IoT based school bus tracking and arrival time prediction" (ICACCI publications, 2017) addresses this issue. "Advanced vehicle monitoring and tracking

system based on raspberry Pi" (Prashanth A. Shinde, Y.B. Mane), presented at the 2015 9th International Conference On Intelligent System And Control (ISCO). Hao Tang, Jian Shi, and Kai Lei are the ones mentioned. at the ICEIEC proceedings, "A Smart low-consumption IoT framework for location tracking and its real application" (2016).

[10]In 2014, ICNSC released a system that K. Sujatha, P. V. Nageswara Rao, K. J. Shruthi, and A. Arjuna Rao developed using the Android platform for bus monitoring.

Article titled "The Internet of Things: A Survey" written by G. Morabito, A. Iera, and L. Atzori and published in 2010 in the journal Computer Networks, volume 54, number 15, pages 2787-2805.

Referenced as [12] is E. A. Lee's 2008 paper "Cyber Physical Systems: Design Challenges" from the 11th IEEE International Symposium on Object-Oriented Real-Time Distributed Computing (ISORC). You may find the document between pages 363 and 369. "Internet of Things for Smart Cities" was an essay authored by A. Zanella, N. Bui, A. Castellani, L. Vangelista, and M. Zorzi that was published in the 2014 issue of the Internet of Things Journal by IEEE. J. Gubbi, R. Buyya, S. Marusic, and M. Palaniswami examine the Internet of Things (IoT) and its prospective uses in their 2013 essay "Internet of Things (IoT): A Vision, Architectural Elements and Future Directions" published in Future Generation Computer Systems.

In a columnar database, multi-node clusters were developed using HDFS by Nresh P., Shekhar GN., Kumar M.K., and Rajyalakshmi P.(2017). Published by Empirical Research Press Ltd. in 2017, this edition is cited on page 186.

[16] Journal for Innovative Development in Pharmaceutical and Technical Science, 2018 edition, Neresh et al., "Implementation of Map Reduce Based Clustering for Large Database

in Cloud." In all, the story covers pages one through four. The article "Towards Smart City: M2M Communications with Software Agent Intelligence" was written by M. Chen and was published in 2013 in the Multimedia Tools and

Applications journal. It can be found on pages 167-198, volume 67, issue 1. This is cited in G. Van Brummelen's Heavenly Mathematics: The Lost Art of Spherical Trigonometry [18]. Princeton University Press, 2013.